

REPEATED IMPACT RESPONSES OF HONEYCOMB SANDWICH PANELS

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ABSTRACT

Ship and offshore structures are frequently subjected to repeated dynamic loadings caused by dropped objects, collisions, grounding, ice floes, slamming. The dynamic deformation accumulation and structural safety of ship and offshore structures under repeated loads are significantly important. Metal honeycomb sandwich panels can possess excellent energy absorption capabilities and have been widely used in the structural impact protection. In this paper, the repeated impact responses of honeycomb sandwich panels were experimentally and numerically investigated. The repeated impact tests of honeycomb sandwich panels were conducted by using the Instron 9350 drop tower. The time histories of impact force and displacement are obtained. The permanent plastic deflections of honeycomb sandwich panels were measured. Besides, a three-dimensional finite element model of a honeycomb sandwich panel under repeated impact loading is established by using the commercial software ABAQUS Explicit and validated by experimental results.

1 INTRODUCTION

Ship and offshore structures are frequently subjected to repeated dynamic loadings such as dropped objects, ice floes as well as slamming loads during voyages and operation, resulting in the dynamic deformation and accumulation damage of marine structures [1-3]. Consequently, it is practically essential to improve impact resistance and energy absorption capacities of ship and offshore structures.

Metal honeycomb sandwich panels can possess excellent energy absorption capabilities, which have been widely used in the structural impact protection and dynamic energy absorption. Current studies on the metal honeycomb sandwich panels are mainly concentrated on their dynamic behaviour and energy absorption mechanisms under single impact loadings [4]. Recently, Balci et al. [5] carried out the single and repeated drop weight impact tests and investigated the dynamic behaviours of repaired honeycomb structures which are used in cargo panels at A319/A320/321. The maintenance effects on the impact resistance levels of honeycomb sandwich structures were performed and compared experimentally. In this paper, the repeated impact responses and energy absorption mechanisms of honeycomb sandwich panels were numerically investigated and validated by repeated drop weight experimental tests.

2 NUMERICAL CALCULATION AND EXPERIMENT

In this paper, the dynamic behaviour of sandwich panel with honeycomb core under repeated impact loadings is numerically investigated by using the commercial software ABAQUS Explicit. The sandwich panel considered here is constituted by top and bottom face sheets as well as aluminium honeycomb core as shown in Figure 1. During our numerical simulations, the geometrical parameters of the honeycomb sandwich panel are defined as follow: The thicknesses of the face sheets and aluminium honeycomb core are defined as 1.4 mm and 15 mm, respectively. The dimension of the square sandwich panel is 180 mm×180 mm. The side length value of regular hexagon honeycomb core is chosen as 4 mm. In addition, an isotropic elastoplastic material model is used for both the mild steel face sheets and aluminium honeycomb core. The stress-strain curves were obtained through the standard in-house uniaxial tension tests. Fixed constraint boundary condition is adopted at top and bottom edges. The face sheets and aluminium honeycomb core are meshed by using the linear reduced integration shell elements. The impact energy of the hammer is defined as 30J.

Figure 1: Numerical model of honeycomb sandwich panel under repeated impact loads

In order to validate the numerical calculation method, the repeated drop weight impact tests were conducted by using INSTRON Drop Tower 9350, as shown in Figure 2. The total impact mass including impact nose, force transducer and the additional mass can be changed from 2.5 kg to 70 kg. The maximum impact velocity can be up to 24 m/s contributing to the spring acceleration system on the top of the impact tower. The hammer with a 40 mm diameter hemispherical nose was connected with a force transducer which has a maximum loading capacity of 90 KN. During the impact tests, all the data were obtained originally from the force transducer and then analyzed by the data acquisition system (DAS 64K) before being exported. During our experimental measurements, the square samples were fixed by the rigid clammer, which was assembled by the upper and lower clammer to achieve fixed boundary condition. The inner dimension of the clamp apparatus was 180 mm×180 mm. The impact energy for each impact was set as 30 J.

Figure 2: Drop weight impact experimental apparatus.

Figure 3(a) shows the time history of impact force for the first impact process. It can be found that the numerical calculation result is in good agreement with the drop weight impact experimental result. However, multiple oscillations occurred in the drop test because of the vibration of the supports and the natural frequencies of the clampers. In addition, sometimes the hammer did not contact with the central part of the previous impact directly during the initial stage of the repeated impact, resulting in some low frequency oscillations at the beginning of the time history of impact force. The permanent deflections of the top face sheet of honeycomb sandwich panel under repeated impact loadings from numerical simulations and experiment measurements are obtained and compared as illustrated in Figure 3(b). One can observe that the permanent deflections of the top face sheet increased with the increase of the impact number. Numerical result is consistent with experimental result.

Figure 3: Comparisons of dynamic responses of honeycomb sandwich panel under repeated impacts.

3 CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this paper, the repeated impact responses of honeycomb sandwich panels were experimentally and numerically investigated. The repeated impact tests of honeycomb sandwich panels were conducted by using the Instron 9350 drop tower. The time histories of impact force are obtained. The permanent deflections of honeycomb sandwich panels were measured. Besides, a three-dimensional finite element model of a honeycomb sandwich panel under repeated impact loading is established by using the commercial software ABAQUS Explicit and validated by experimental results.

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